

Influence of Selected Social Media on Lipeño Young Adult's Travel Decisions

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Abstract

In today's digital age, social media plays a vital role in everyone's life. Social media, in terms of tourism, helps travelers in finding information before, during and after their travels. The purpose of this paper is to assess the influence of social media on the travel decisions of young Lipeños in terms of information, promotion, and communication. This paper also determines what social media platform is the most influential to these Lipeños travel decisions.

Keywords: social media, young adult, travel decisions

INTRODUCTION

The use of social media has become popular among digital natives in the past decade. It continues to gain popularity as its features develop, being more than a platform for communication. Social media initially existed to help users virtually connect with other individuals, but it has evolved into a vital 21st-century marketing tool. Before the emergence of social media, travelers used to rely on advice or opinions from relatives, friends, traditional travel companies, and print media to get information about the destinations they were interested in. Travelers now utilize social media channels to pull from peer experiences to get inspiration for their future travel destinations and help them decide where to go and what to do once they get there (Golla, 2020).

The younger generation of Asian consumers is becoming a force. By 2025, Generation Z will account for a quarter of the Asia-Pacific (APAC) region's population, the same proportion as millennials. As one of the most important consumer segments in the near future, the rise of Gen Z is expected to have a dramatic impact in Asia (Digital Business Lab, 2021). They rely on social media but are thoughtful about how they engage with it. For Gen Z, social media is primarily used for information, leisure, and entertainment purposes. They are much more active in planning their trips on the internet as they search for information from the beginning to the end of the travel decision-making process (Nguyen, et al., 2021).

Tourists are becoming consumers as well as producers by generating their posts and blogs on tourist spots. The online comments, pictures, and captions of tourist spots, profiles and facts with different experiences shared by tourists generate trust and eagerness among new users (Rahman & Begum, 2020). Modern tourists have more trust in other traveler's opinions using social media rather than official marketing advice (Živković, et al., 2014).

While social networking sites and mobile applications can be standardized products, the way users interact with them varies greatly by culture (Dimitriou & AbouElgheit, 2019). The influence of social media on travel decision-making has attracted so much attention from Generation Z. As a noteworthy trend, social media is rapidly becoming a primary source of information and impressions about tourist destinations. Travelers, especially the Generation Z, are using intensively the information from the web in their decisions and have widely adopted social media to seek advice, share, and annotate their experiences.

The role of social media in tourism is to inspire and engage. It has made a huge impact on the tourism industry, which is seen in the ways people research before going on a trip. Social media started to be an inevitable part in travel planning due to people searching for content and interacting with others, while being influenced with their decisions (Dusiková, 2018). Thus, social media has transformed the way people make decisions (Tas, 2020). Each platform of social media has become an excellent resource for gathering information about destinations, accommodations, activities, dining, and more.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

This study was conducted to assess the influence of social media on the travel decisions of young adult Lipeños. Specifically, it aimed to answer the following:

1. What is the profile of respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 sex;
 - 1.3 civil status;
 - 1.4 educational attainment;
 - 1.5 employment status;
 - 1.6 monthly household income; and,
 - 1.7 social media platforms they use?
2. How does social media influence young adult Lipeños' travel decisions in terms of:
 - 2.1 information;
 - 2.2 promotion; and,
 - 2.3 communication?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the profile of respondents and the influence of social media to their travel decisions?
4. What recommendations may be proposed to tourism establishments to attract more young adult travelers?

LITERATURE REVIEW

In the age of social media, consumers prefer to source information from third parties that they deem to be objective and reliable. The most popular content related to travel is generated by users themselves or influencers (Smith, 2021). Carey (2021) noted that more people are using platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and Youtube to figure out where they should go next. Instagram's geographic and trending hashtags make it simple for users to find exactly what they're looking for. Apollo Digital Agency (2020), on the other hand, recognizes sites such as TripAdvisor, along Facebook and Twitter as the most popular mediums for travel-related research. The market study of European Travel Commission (2020) revealed that image-dominated platforms, such as Instagram and Pinterest, are the most common source for travel inspiration.

The young adults of this century are part of Generation Z. Also known as Gen Z, iGen, or centennials, it refers to the generation born between 1997-2012, following millennials. (Meola, 2021). Kasasa (2021) stated that Gen Z have grown up in a hyper-connected world and the smartphone is their preferred method of communication. Gen Z is heavily influenced by photos and videos and as a result, social media platforms have an immense influence on their choices as consumers (ETC, 2020). Monaco (2017) found that Gen Z use almost exclusively the web to find the information needed to make purchasing decisions and to make reservations. They query online friends or use contacts they have in social networks. Similarly, The Annie E. Casey Foundation (2021) revealed that Gen Z rely on their tech savvy and extensive social networks to make informed purchasing decisions.

The Expedia Group Media Solutions analysis shows that 84% of Generation Z believe that social media plays an important role when travelling (Generation Y: 77%) and over 50% use platforms such as Twitter, Snapchat, Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube when planning and during the trip. A 2019 research by Booking.com reveals that Instagram is the most popular source of inspiration when choosing a vacation destination among Gen Z. 70% enjoy seeing travel posts and photos on social media. When it comes to picking which countries to visit, they turn to their social feeds for inspiration, with 44% citing it as their primary source of travel inspiration. Gen Z are also interested in travelling in places that look good in pictures; 57% of them say that they always upload pictures from their trips on social media.

In the context of tourism, social media are one of the most commonly used information sources. The credibility of information sources is one of the fundamental elements that visitors are taking into consideration while they plan to visit a certain destination. Social media attracts the attention of customers since online reviews and recommendations by tourists are perceived to have a higher credibility than conventional visitor information sources (Berhanu & Raj, 2020). The time spent searching for travel information has been reduced by social media use. Thus, it has become a highly influential source of information to tourists as they have entirely changed how tourists search, collect and disseminate travel information and experiences. Since people trust word of mouth when making important decisions, social media sites have become another avenue for people to share

vital information (Kruger & Manyever, 2019).

Aside from verbal information, consumers seek visual information on destinations. With fast evolving technology and sites and applications like Instagram, users are able to post photos and videos on the Internet. Although photos play an important role on people's decision-making, they want to see whether the photos correspond to the reviews written of the product or destination. People read reviews and comments made by other travellers (Terttunen, 2017).

Social media plays a significant role in marketing communication campaigns for tourism organizations for both informative and promotion tools and increases unique visitor for official websites and blogs (Kavoura & Stavrianea, 2015, as cited in Tran et al., 2017). Because of its integrated communications, social media has become a very successful platform for tourism promotion. Tourism promotion on social media has become a significant instrument for attracting tourists' attention, and tourist managers should develop a tourism promotion strategy that is appropriate for their enterprises (Javed, Tucková, & Jibril, 2020). The majority of places throughout the world now use social media channels to sell their products and services (Deccan, 2021). They use these platforms to give tourists enough information to help them improve their travel plans. The adoption of social media as a strategic tool provides a platform to promote tactical revenue management strategies and to practice differential pricing motives (Ampountolas et al., 2019). Social networks facilitate the development of a closer relationship with customers, who can then get involved in promoting tourist destinations or holiday offers.

On-line oral communication, also known as e-Word of Mouth (eWOM), is considered the foundation for any online action or engagement (Dionysopoulou & Mylonakis, 2013). In the tourism sector, social media has transformed communication. It allowed people to communicate with one another based on their shared interests. The electronic Word-of-mouth or eWOM communication is central to the social media such that the power of expression lies with the content creator, who then passes it on to the members of their group, who then pass it on to other members, giving the communication a sense of virality (Kakirala & Singh, 2020). The eWOM can enhance visitor satisfaction due to product or service improvement. It can also solve problems and doubts during travel and can help discover what tourists think and say about their experience (Živković, et al., 2014). The eWOM and visual information of travel destinations in these kinds of platforms are valuable and might play a crucial role influencing consumer perception on the destination and decision-making (Terttunen, 2017).

Sabanaeva (2017) also identified a number of factors that contribute to users' increasing reliance on social media platforms as critical sources of travel information. The platforms' dependability, reliability, honesty, sincerity, and trustworthiness are among them. The data analysis of Hajli (2014) showed that social media-encouraged trust significantly impacts purchase intent and the other perceived usefulness. The study also showed that perceived influence is more than trust on intention to buy on social networking sites. However, additional data analysis revealed that trust indirectly influenced perceived usefulness. In comparison, the findings of Nguyen, Truong, Pham, Tran, and Nguyen (2021) indicate that Gen Z values the usefulness of social media the most, followed by perceived value, and finally, information trustworthiness.

METHODS

Research Design. Convenience sampling is a type of sampling where the members of the sample who are conveniently available are selected. The researcher used convenience sampling due to COVID-19 pandemic that limited the distribution capability of the researcher.

Respondents of the Study. The respondents of this research were comprised of 300 young adults aged 20-24 residing in thirty selected barangays of Lipa City: Adya, Anilao, Balintawak, Bolbok, Bulacnin, Calamias, Dagatan, Inosloban, Kayumanggi, Latag, Lodlod, Lumbang, Malitlit, Maraway, Mataas na Lupa, Pagolingin West, Pangao, Pinagkawitan, Plaridel, Poblacion Brgy. 1, Poblacion Brgy. 10, Sabang, Sampaguita, San Jose, San Lucas, Santo Toribio, Sapac, Sico, Talisay, and Tambo.

Data Gathering Instrument. A self-made questionnaire was used in gathering data. The questionnaire has two parts. The first part determined the profile of respondents in terms of age, sex, barangay, civil status, educational attainment, monthly household income, and types of social media they use. The other part focuses on the respondents' evaluation of the following influence factors such as information, promotion, and communication. Each factor comprised of three to four (3-4) items.

The instrument was structured on a 4 - point Likert scale, scale ranging from 4 (Strongly Agree), 3 (Agree), 2 (Disagree), and 1 (Strongly disagree). To identify the influence of social media on Lipeño young adults' travel decisions, the following scale of mean ranges were used to interpret the computed weighted mean and composite mean: $3.51 - 4.00 = 4$, $2.50 - 3.50 = 3$, $1.51 - 2.50 = 2$, and $1.00 - 1.50 = 1$.

Data Analysis. The survey results were analyzed using the following statistical treatment: Frequency and Percentage. These were used to calculate the distribution of respondents based on various person-related variables.

Weighted Mean. This was used to determine the assessment of the respondents with regards to their data set.

Chi-Square Test. This was the statistical instrument used to test the relationship between the respondents according to their demographic profile and the influence of social media to their travel decisions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

As the online world continues to transform the way destinations are researched, viewed, and sold, it is becoming increasingly important to understand the value of efficiently utilizing these tools and channels. Social media has helped tourists identify their preferred destination and determine what activities to engage with in advance.

Table 1. Profile of Respondents

Profile	Category	Frequency and Percentage
Age	20 years old	68, 22.67
	21 years old	104, 34.67
	22 years old	63, 21.00
	23 years old	32, 10.66
	24 years old	33, 11.00
Sex	Male	102, 34.00
	Female	198, 66.00
Civil Status	Single	291, 97.00
	Married	9, 3.00
Educational Attainment	High school	96, 32.00
	Technical/Vocational	41, 13.67
	Bachelor's degree	161, 43.67
	Master's degree	2, 0.66
Employment Status	Full-time employee	65, 21.67
	Part-time employee	19, 6.33
	Self-employed	11, 3.67
	Unemployed	16, 5.33
	Student	189, 63.00
Family Monthly Income	PhP 10,000 and below	113, 37.67
	PhP 10,001 – PhP 15,000	82, 27.33
	PhP 15,001 – PhP 25,000	50, 16.67
	PhP 25,001 – PhP 35,000	26, 8.66
	Above PhP 35,000	29, 9.67

The study revealed that 34.7 percent or 104 respondents were 21 years old, 22.67 percent or 68 respondents were 20 years old, 21 percent or 63 respondents were 22 years old, while 11 percent or 33 respondents were 24 years old. Finally, there were 10.66 percent or 32 respondents who were 23 years old.

In terms of sex, most of the respondents were female, with a total number of 198 or 66 percent. On the other hand, there were a total of 102 male respondents or 34 percent of the population.

In terms of civil status, 97 percent out of 300 respondents were single and there were only nine (9) respondents or three (3) percent who were married. As for educational attainment, 161 respondents or 53.67 percent attained bachelor's degree, 96 or 32 percent reached high school, 41 or 13.67 percent took technical/vocational course, and two (2) respondents or 0.66 percent finished a master's degree.

Majority of the respondents were students, with a total number of 189 or 63 percent. 65 respondents or 21.67 percent were full-time employees while part-timers were 19 or 6.33 percent. There were 16 or 5.33 percent unemployed respondents and 11 or 3.67 percent self-employed respondents.

113 or 37.67 percent of the respondents have a household monthly income of Php 10,000 and below, 82

or 27.33 percent earns Php 10,001 - 15,000. Meanwhile, those whose family earn between Php 25,000 – Php 35,000 monthly represented 26 or 8.66 percent. Only 29 or 9.67 percent earns above Php 35,000.

Table 2. Frequency of Using Social Media Platforms to Read or Look for Travel-Related Content

Social Media Platform	Weighted Mean	Rank
Facebook	6.51	1
Twitter	3.84	5
Instagram	4.73	3
YouTube	5.71	2
TikTok	4.68	4
Reddit	1.64	7
TripAdvisor	1.68	6

Legend:

6.51-7.00 – Daily	2.51-3.50 – 4-6 times a month
5.51-6.50 – 4-6 times a week	1.51-2.50 – 2-3 times a month
4.51-5.50 – 2-3 times a week	1.00-1.50 – Never
3.51-4.50 – Once a month	

Majority of the respondents spent the most time on Facebook to read or look for travel-related content. It was followed by YouTube and Instagram platforms. Meanwhile, they spent the least amount of time on the platform Reddit.

Table 3. Assessment on the Influence of Social Media in terms of Information

STATEMENT	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
<i>When I see travel-related content on social media...</i>		
1. I find the videos and images of the destinations eye-catching.	3.63	Strongly Agree
2. I want to visit the featured destinations.	3.57	Strongly Agree
3. it influences me to make changes with my existing travel plans.	3.37	Agree
4. it influences how long I will stay at a destination I want to visit.	3.31	Agree
Composite Mean	3.47	Influential

As shown in the table, the statement that garnered the highest mean of 3.63 was “I find the videos and images of the destinations eye-catching,” with the verbal interpretation of strongly agree. The statement “I want to visit the featured destinations” obtained the second highest mean of 3.57 with an interpretation strongly agree as well. On the other hand, the statement “it influences how long I will stay at a destination I want to visit” got the lowest mean of 3.31, yet it was interpreted as agree.

Table 4. Assessment on the Influence of Social Media in terms of Promotion

STATEMENT <i>I am more likely to...</i>	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. be aware of the destinations posted on social media compared to other medium of promotion.	3.46	Agree
2. visit a destination posted on social media than other medium of promotion.	3.34	Agree
3. avail products or services of tourism establishments posted on social media than other medium of promotion.	3.19	Agree
4. choose to avail the product or services of a tourism establishment that is active on social media.	3.33	Agree
Composite Mean	3.33	Influential

Based on the table, the statement “be aware of the destinations posted on social media compared to other medium of promotion” received the highest mean of 3.46 with the verbal interpretation of agree, following the statement “visit a destination posted on social media than other medium of promotion” with the mean of 3.34, that was also interpreted agree. Meanwhile, the statement that got the lowest mean of 3.19 was “avail products or services of tourism establishments posted on social media than other medium of promotion” yet interpreted agree.

Table 5. Assessment on Influence of Social Media in terms of Communication

STATEMENT <i>My travel decisions are influenced by...</i>	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. experiences of other tourists posted on social media	3.51	Strongly agree
2. reviews on a destination posted on social media.	3.53	Strongly agree
3. recommendations posted on social media.	3.48	Agree
Composite Mean	3.51	Highly influential

As set out in the table, the statement that garnered the highest mean of 3.53 was “reviews on a destination posted on social media,” which was interpreted as strongly agree. The statement “experiences of other tourists posted on social media” received the second highest mean of 3.51 and was also interpreted as strongly agree. On the other hand, the statement that obtained the lowest mean of 3.48 yet was interpreted agree was “recommendations posted on social media.”

Table 6. Summary Table of Composite Mean

Influence of social media in terms of...	Composite Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. Information	3.47	Influential
2. Promotion	3.33	Influential
3. Communication	3.51	Highly Influential
Grand Composite Mean	3.44	Influential

As illustrated in the table, influence of social media in terms of communication attained the highest composite mean of 3.51. It is followed by promotion, with the composite mean of 3.47. Meanwhile, the lowest composite mean was 3.33 was their assessment on influence of social media in terms of promotion.

Based on the results in the Table 7, the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, employment status, and monthly household income has no significant relationship with the influence of selected social media platforms to their travel decisions.

Table 7. Correlation Analysis between the Respondents' Profile and the Influence of Selected Social Media to their Travel Decisions

Variable	Degrees of Freedom	Chi-square value	P-Value	Conclusion
Age	8	6.680	0.572	Not Significant
Sex	2	1.133	0.568	Not Significant
Civil Status	2	1.465	0.481	Not Significant
Educational Attainment	6	6.332	0.387	Not Significant
Employment Status	8	3.620	0.890	Not Significant
Monthly Household Income	8	7.733	0.460	Not Significant

Conclusions

Most of the respondents were female, 21 years old, single, attained a bachelor's degree, earn a monthly household income of Php 10,000 and below and were students. They spend 2-4 hours on social media daily, use Facebook for looking and reading travel-related content and are very much influenced by the social media platform in their travel decisions.

In terms of information, tourism establishments can utilize Facebook where most young adults are active to share valuable information about the featured destination as well as their brand. This will allow tourism establishments to be easily seen by their intended audience. In terms of promotion, tourism establishments must develop a trustworthy brand image not just on their actual premises but also on social media platforms. Using top social media platforms used by young adults such as Facebook, YouTube, and Instagram in promoting their offerings can encourage potential customers to choose them. It would be better if they continually enhance the actual products and services in this regard to avoid disappointments from young adult customers.

In terms of communication, one of the best ways to encourage young adult travelers is to share experiences and reviews or feedbacks of tourists who have purchased their services. Tourists' feedback is essential because it can retain customers and attract new ones. They must also regularly engage with young adult travelers in order to foster a favorable relationship with these people and gain them visibility. As a result, present and future young adult travelers will share good information about them, boosting their market profile as destinations of choice. Moreover, establishing connection with young adult travelers will assist tourism establishments in learning about their strengths and weaknesses, allowing them for opportunity and development.

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